

Harnessing Spatial Selections: A Guide to SGIS's Select by Layer Tool

The 'Select by Layer' tool in SGIS Desktop and SGIS v.R is a powerful feature that allows users to select features based on their spatial relationships to other features in a different layer.

The "Select by Layer" function is helpful because it lets users automatically select features based on spatial criteria, rather than having to manually pick them. This saves time and boosts efficiency, especially when working with large datasets.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the tool, we'll provide an example solution for each spatial relationship criterion.

1. Spatial Relationship Criterion #1: Points in Polygons

Fig.1 Data loaded into SGIS Desktop version 1.2.

To illustrate the Point in Polygons criterion, we'll use some example data. We have a telecommunications dataset that includes three distinct polygon areas, each connected to a telecommunication distribution cabinet. Within all three polygons, there are point features located across four different layers.

For our first example, we'll focus on the Residen_hh Point layer. The user wants to filter all Residen points located inside Polygon Area 1, then those in Polygon Area 2, and finally, those in Polygon Area 3.

To do this quickly and effectively, we need to access the "Select By Layer" tool. You can find this tool in the Selection menu on the main toolbar, as well as in the toolbox located at the top of the user interface.

Let's start by clicking on the function.

Fig. 2. To easily access the 'Select by Layer' function, it is located in the main menu toolbar as well as in the Selection menu.

Fig. 3. The dialog window with three dropdown options: Selection Mode for spatial relationship criteria, the 'Layer to be selected,' and the 'Layer acting as the condition' for the spatial relationship.

Once the function is activated, a dialog window will pop up. Here, users are prompted to choose the Selection Mode from a dropdown list, which includes all the spatial relationship criteria. We'll select the criterion that's appropriate for our example.

Next, users need to pick the 'Layer that will be selected.'

This step sets up the spatial relationship criterion between two different layers, so it's important to specify which layer's features we want to select.

The third dropdown lets users choose the 'Layer that will act as the condition,' which defines the spatial relationship between the two layers. Let's start with the first selection.

Fig. 4. Selecting the 'Points in Polygons' option from the dropdown list, enabling the selection of point features located within one or more polygons.

We'll choose the first option from the dropdown list—Points in Polygons. This option lets us select point features that are found within one or more polygons. In other words, the Polygon layer can have multiple polygons.

Fig. 5. Selecting the 'point-Residen' layer from the second dropdown list to highlight Residen points located inside Area 1.

Next, we need to open the second dropdown list to choose the layer that contains the features we want to select and highlight. In our example, we want to select all Residen points located inside Area 1, so we'll choose the 'point-Residen' layer.

Fig. 6. Selecting the 'Condition Layer' as 'Polygon Area 1' before clicking 'Select' to complete the setup.

Naturally, the third dropdown option, the 'Condition Layer,' will be the layer for 'Polygon Area 1.' With these three settings configured, we just need to click on 'Select'.

Fig. 7. The point features that meet this spatial criterion are immediately selected and highlighted in the Graphics Panel.

Fig. 8. Selected points highlighted in lime green, with the option for users to customize the highlight color to their preference.

The points are highlighted in lime green, but this is a setting that users can customize to their liking.

The selected points can now be easily exported into a separate GIS layer for further processing. For instance, users can later open the attribute table and add new attribute fields to include relevant information.

Fig. 9. Using the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function to create a new layer containing the previously selected features.

To do this, we'll use the 'Selected Elements in New Layer' function.

This handy feature lets us create a new layer that includes the features we previously selected based on our chosen conditions. Let's go ahead and click on it.

The function prompts us to enter a name for the new layer we're creating. We'll name it 'Residen Points in Polygon 1,' as those are the points we were looking for.

Fig. 10. The function prompts us to enter a name for the new layer, which we'll call 'Residen Points in Polygon 1,' as these are the points we want.

We click 'OK,' and with that, a new layer is created. The procedure is now complete.

Fig.11 The procedure is complete.